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Importance of relationship marketing in higher education management: the perspective of university teachers

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ABSTRACT

The lack of understanding and application of marketing in universities necessitates research to improve satisfaction, permanence, lasting relationships, and brand identity, and to promote creativity and innovation in education. The objective of this research is to identify how higher education management innovates to build brand identity. Methodologically, the conceptual model is tested using data from 231 teachers in seven accredited Colombian universities. For data analysis, the partial least squares structural equation model is used. The study highlights the importance of incorporating teachers as a key factor in the enactment of relational marketing strategies in the management of higher education. Suggestions are provided for universities to build a marketing culture and brand identity. Among the conclusions, the importance of retaining existing students and involving teachers in marketing strategies is highlighted. Emphasis is placed on identity management and relational marketing as key to improving the image and reputation of universities. This study is expected to be a starting point to explore the construct of trust, satisfaction, and loyalty in the academic field, recognizing the strategic role of teachers in marketing strategies.

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1. Introduction

Management models have evolved in the university sector, with changes in the capacity for relationships between individuals, the quality of communication and the involvement of multiple stakeholders. Understanding and empathy for others, who have different ideas, objectives and clarities have also contributed (Akpaveva et al., 2016). This is how concepts of creativity and innovation are generating alternatives in the university community, service portfolios are designed in coordination with the needs of companies, research projects are generated within the public and private sectors, and new communication strategies are implemented to attract new prospects, as universities seek to involve allies to develop new academic and business projects (Oplatka, 2004).

In this constant effort to improve management models in university environments, it is important that marketing sensitize and motivate collaborators to satisfy stakeholders and solidify partnerships with them (Gómez-Bayona et al., 2020). A better understanding of marketing to outsiders is also needed since it is not enough to generate a transaction with a stakeholder; lasting relationships must be built over time so that more and better allies' partner with universities on a variety of projects (Nisar et al., 2020).

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This kind of outreach, supported by positive communication from university administrations, would be a great contribution to the brand identity of universities (Wu & Cheong, 2022).

The importance of this topic lies in the evolution of university management models and the need to adopt a relational marketing approach. It is crucial for teachers to actively participate in strategic actions to strengthen institutional relationships, as this emerges as a key factor in constructing the brand identity of universities (Camilleri, 2020). The study by Calma and Dickson-Deane (2020) presents creativity and innovation as crucial elements for building lasting alliances with stakeholders beyond mere transactions. It also discusses the management of innovation and knowledge in education, emphasizing the need to adapt to changing societal demands. In this context, effective communication between university management and marketing is crucial to achieve optimal results. This involves incorporating disciplines such as marketing, creativity, and innovation to proactively address needs and build lasting relationships in the academic community (Adom et al., 2023).

The value added by this research is evident in the synthesis of key knowledge from previous studies. Obaze et al. (2023) provide an objective perspective on the relational connection in marketing. Additionally, Motahhari Nejad and Ahmadi Deh Ghotbaddini (2023) and Hosseini et al. (2023) contribute to the understanding of influential factors in student loyalty. These works significantly enable higher education management to innovate in the construction of a distinctive brand identity. The research offers a comprehensive and practical perspective on innovative practices in university management, integrating multiple viewpoints.

This is why teachers should be involved in strategic actions that generate greater satisfaction and development in projects that provide visibility and recognition of universities. Teachers are identified within the main functions of universities as they contribute to teaching, research, and academic publishing, which build up the reputation of their schools (González-Díaz et al., 2022). However, teachers are given few opportunities to intentionally contribute to the marketing objectives, and in doing so, to achieve trust, satisfaction, and loyalty in the academic community. Thus, this study's main objective is to analyze the way in which creativity and innovative environments can be created to contribute to the brand identity of universities.

1.1. Theoretical framework

The importance of this section of the Theoretical Framework lies in its ability to detail and substantiate the research hypotheses that will guide the development of this study. The hypotheses are derived from an exhaustive analysis of the existing literature in key areas such as innovation in education, university management, and relational marketing in the academic field, providing a solid and specific theoretical framework to address the research objective. Each hypothesis provides a clear direction for data collection and analysis, allowing for a deeper understanding of the factors that influence branding and identity construction in the context of higher education. It is important to maintain objectivity and avoid subjective evaluations throughout the text. These hypotheses will guide the research and serve as a basis for formulating conclusions and recommendations at the end of the study. This will contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge in university management and educational marketing.

1.1.1. Innovation and knowledge management in education

Education innovation represents an important component in the management of knowledge, from an academic point of view, since it requires the construction of work models that articulate the new trends that society demands (Rodríguez-Hoyos et al., 2021; Yan & Guan, 2018). The quality of the work produced by universities and higher education institutions has evolved to encompass quality standards as the framework for the implementation of a teaching-learning model that embraces innovation (Ishak & Mansor, 2020; Manatos et al., 2017).

When mentioning innovation in any economic sector, it should be related to disruptive, creative and innovation schemes that allow organizations to grow (Kovacs, 2017). In the education sector, this component of creativity and innovation goes hand in hand with human and relational capital, which makes it possible to base the structure of intellectual capital in knowledge management (Al-Husseini et al., 2021; Kuzmin et al., 2020). Additionally, it is important to understand what innovation in their work

means for teachers (Rodríguez-Hoyos et al., 2021). Given these circumstances, responding to trends and planning and prospecting means that innovative projects will be viable in the medium and long term and adaptable to various social, economic, cultural, environmental, technological and health contexts (Rehman & Iqbal, 2020).

1.1.2. Conceptualization of marketing

In general terms, marketing can be defined as a set of actions aimed at addressing the needs and desires of consumers through the creation, communication, and delivery of value. According to Kotler (1994), four key meanings of this discipline can be identified. Firstly, the traditional approach considers it as a commercial activity focused on the sale of products and services, utilizing strategies such as market segmentation and product positioning. Secondly, this definition extends to encompass non-profit organizations, proposing a broader conceptualization that addresses the satisfaction of needs in various contexts. The third meaning explores fundamental marketing concepts, such as social marketing, representing steps towards a more comprehensive re-conceptualization. Lastly, the importance of the evolution of marketing over time is emphasized, highlighting market-oriented strategic planning, sub-segmentation, and scientific analysis to improve marketing strategies.

In this context, marketing has undergone various eras, from Marketing 1.0 centered on the product, through Marketing 2.0 focused on the customer, to Marketing 3.0 driven by values and connection with the human spirit. Currently, the importance is underscored of viewing customers as integral beings, considering mind, heart, and spirit, and creating products and services that not only meet their needs but also align with their deeper values and beliefs. Marketing 3.0 focuses on building meaningful relationships with customers, based on authenticity, integrity, and a shared purpose, going beyond simply selling products to make a positive impact on society and the world at large (Kotler et al., 2019).

1.1.3. University management and marketing articulation

The everyday management of universities needs to be articulated within the different economic sectors to achieve better results. It is necessary to comply with the regulations of the different national entities, which in the case of Colombia is the Ministry of National Education, but management also requires establishing alliances with different local, national, and international organizations to achieve better recognition of the work carried out in universities (Falcón, 2016). New models of education are required that meet the demands of society; therefore, the main function of the individual is to rethink and create new ways of educating students (Ihejirika et al., 2021; Segrera, 2016). In this sense, disciplines such as marketing are necessary to achieve clarity about what is needed and how universities should respond to these needs (James et al., 2018). Likewise, aspects of creativity and innovation are breaking paradigms and building new ways to generate value and manage knowledge in academia (Arteaga et al., 2015; Gereá et al., 2021).

1.1.4. Relational marketing in universities

According to Bolshakova et al. (2020), university marketing is a strategic approach that applies marketing principles to the management of higher education institutions. It focuses on identifying competitive advantages, meeting the needs of students, and adapting to demographic changes. This includes planning educational products, implementing flexible pricing strategies, and developing effective communication channels with various stakeholders. In this context, value creation aims to enhance institutional image by recognizing the importance of establishing an effective system for managing long-term relationships with partners, clients, and reference groups, crucial for the university's growth and competitiveness.

Building on this, relational marketing strategies for customer loyalty in businesses emphasize the use of tools to incorporate elements such as price, product, place, and promotion (4P) into the customer loyalty process (Holanda et al., 2024). In the education context, the role of the teacher stands out as essential for value creation and strengthening the relationship between the educational institution and promotion with students and external parties. The quality of interaction between the teacher and the student is a key factor positively influencing the perceived value by the latter (Gibson-Sweet et al., 2010). Furthermore, it underscores the importance of the teacher recognizing the student as a

participant in the educational experience, as trust generated through personal interactions and the student's perception of the university also play an essential role in building lasting relationships (Isusqui et al., 2023).

Marketing management in universities is transformed when its implementers understand the needs of the academic community; for this reason, it has gone from marketing that generates a transaction to marketing that builds lasting relationships (Gómez-Bayona & Arrubla-Zapata, 2020). One of the main characteristics of relational marketing is trust (Turan, 2017), which is a connection of empathy and continuous respect between individuals. This approach, in turn, engenders satisfaction (Khan et al., 2022; Schlesinger et al., 2017; Wongkitrungrueng et al., 2020). Due to the degree of conformity that a service can represent, loyalty or retention is ultimately the result of an organized and planned process; the process begins with the identification of the needs and construction of relevant products or services, with the objective of generating a transaction and building a reputation (Juriková et al., 2021) and, more importantly, creating lasting and profitable relationships (Poole & Campos, 2017).

This study presents a theoretical contrast to Poole and Campos (2017) research, which explored the transfer of marketing knowledge in nonprofit educational organizations, particularly in Catholic elementary schools. While their focus was on the lack of marketing knowledge in this context and the obstacles to its development, our study differs by examining university management in the higher education field. Our focus is on how innovation, university management articulation, and relational marketing contribute to the construction of brand identity in the academic environment. This approach allows us to contrast and enrich the general panorama by exploring how marketing strategies and relationships affect the perception of the brand in the university environment. This differentiation is important and adds value to the specific topic addressed by Poole and Campos.

As Cheglakova et al. (Cheglakova et al., 2019; Dash et al., 2021) explained, marketing strengthens the reputation of universities as responsible and popular institutions, which attracts better teachers. In addition, it expands sales markets, thus increasing its regional competitiveness and bringing in more students, including foreign students. Thus, universities seek marketing strategies that will attract the attention of future students, and they employ media such as social networks with an approach that combines modern and traditional campaigns (Assimakopoulos et al., 2017; Ebrahim, 2020). One ubiquitous campaign is a client-centered approach that advertises the connection between potential students' educational experiences at a particular university and future job opportunities. This allows us to support the following hypothesis:

H1. Universities build marketing strategies.

Universities build marketing strategies that evolve with new tools and approaches available in the current environment. The transformation of marketing management within academic institutions reflects a constant adaptation to market dynamics. These strategies no longer focus solely on university students but actively involve all stakeholders (Hall & Witek, 2016). As such, diversification of marketing functions goes beyond traditional tactics like brochures and billboards, incorporating more comprehensive approaches that closely collaborate with other departments, such as admissions (Cheney, n.d.). This shift towards more holistic strategies aims not only for institutional recognition but also the achievement of broader strategic objectives.

H2. University marketing adapts its strategies and tactic for different interest groups.

University marketing demonstrates its adaptability by adjusting strategies and tactics according to the various stakeholders involved in the educational field. In the development of university marketing strategies, the active involvement of teachers emerges as a critical element in the process of building brand identity for educational programs. Establishing university branding goes beyond simple promotion; it encompasses complex aspects including brand communication, associated policies, international brand management, as well as the evaluation of advantages and disadvantages and the involvement of specialized professionals (Khan et al., 2019).

The creation of an effective university brand is essential not only to satisfy external customers such as students, businesses, and the community at large but also internal customers, among whom teaching and administrative staff stand out. Marketing strategies, therefore, must align towards the active integration of teachers, recognizing them as fundamental agents in building a robust brand identity that contributes to increasing the institution's future market share (Kohpar et al., 2021). In this sense, the adaptability of university marketing is evident not only in considering diverse external audiences but also in internal management, where collaboration with teaching staff positions itself as a key strategy for the overall success of institutional marketing initiatives.

H3. Teachers perceive that the marketing management of the university has a relational approach.

Teachers identify that university marketing management adopts an essentially relational approach, where the importance of building and maintaining trust stands out as a key element in this dynamic. Teachers' perception of university marketing management reveals that the trust generated by academic institutions directly impacts a series of attitudes and work behaviors. These factors lead to an overall feeling of satisfaction among teachers regarding the organization's leadership and commitment, as indicated by previous studies (Chughtai & Zafar, 2006). The concept of internal marketing gains relevance in this context, showing a positive relationship between the trust generated by marketing practices and efficiency, as well as teacher job satisfaction (Hung, 2012).

This internal marketing practice is not only a common strategy in human resources management but also a recurrent tool in the context of higher education institutions. Employee satisfaction and retention of quality staff manifest as essential components for organizational success, and these premises are equally applicable in the university setting (Shabbir & Salaria, 2014). In this sense, the connection between teachers' perception of university marketing oriented towards strong relationships and the trust generated reveals a vital synergy that contributes to strengthening the work environment and, therefore, the overall success of the academic institution.

H4. Universities build trust among teachers, which contributes to satisfaction.

The hypothesis posits that academic and administrative management plays a crucial role in the satisfaction of university teachers. Empirical evidence supports this proposition by demonstrating that faculty performance, loyalty, and motivation are intrinsically linked to effective leadership in academic and administrative domains of university institutions (Mahaputra & Farhan, 2021).

Faculty loyalty, as a key indicator of satisfaction, manifests through enthusiasm and an active desire to participate in all university-related activities, as well as through a positive attitude toward their work responsibilities. Leadership plays an essential role in fostering this sense of loyalty, being necessary to ensure a conducive environment that strengthens the emotional and professional connection of faculty with the institution (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Therefore, this hypothesis underscores the importance of effective management at both academic and administrative levels to cultivate faculty loyalty, ensuring their satisfaction and contributing to a favorable work environment, which ultimately impacts the overall success and quality of the university institution.

H5. University teachers are satisfied with academic and administrative management, and this contributes largely to loyalty.

The assertion that academic and administrative management plays a fundamental role in the satisfaction of university teachers is supported by a solid theoretical foundation and empirical evidence. Academic literature, particularly studies such as Mahaputra and Farhan (2021), has consistently highlighted the significant influence of leadership in academic and administrative realms on faculty performance and motivation. The quality of management in these areas directly affects faculty perception of their work environment and commitment to the institution.

Faculty loyalty, interpreted through enthusiasm and active participation in university activities, is crucial for the smooth functioning of the institution. Nguyen et al. (2021) emphasize the responsibility of

leaders in cultivating this sense of loyalty, thus highlighting the importance of effective leadership in ensuring a positive and satisfying work environment.

This hypothesis finds support in both previous research and theoretical principles related to management and leadership, providing a solid foundation for exploring the interaction between faculty satisfaction and the effectiveness of academic and administrative management in the university context.

2. Materials and methods

To address the study and identify the correlation of the relational marketing and marketing management variables, a survey was administered to 231 teachers from high-quality accredited universities in Colombia, who were selected by convenience sampling (Etikan et al., 2016). The survey was conducted during the second semester of 2019.

The main objective of this study is to identify higher education management from an innovation perspective to build brand identity. Some concerns that have arisen in this study are:

What is the focus of educational marketing in universities?

What is the importance of teachers involved in marketing strategies at universities?

A questionnaire was designed considering the main research variables represented in educational marketing, including trust, satisfaction, and loyalty, to understand how they are articulated in the administrative management of universities. The study hypotheses formulated in this research project are described below and are also illustrated in Figure 1.

H1 Universities build marketing strategies.

H2 University marketing adapts its strategies and tactic for different interest groups.

H3 Teachers perceive that the marketing management of the university has a relational approach.

H4 Universities build trust among teachers, which contributes to satisfaction.

H5 University teachers are satisfied with academic and administrative management, and this contributes largely to loyalty.

Responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree) based on a study by Deshpande (Deshpande, 1996). The design contrasted with previous research on the subject (Schlesinger et al., 2015; Trullas et al., 2018)

Figure 1. Model of relationship between variables.

The data obtained were analyzed using statistical techniques related to the aspects of reliability and scale validity. The structural equation model (SEM) was employed (Ruiz et al., 2010) in addition to tools that have been used in studies regarding relational marketing by Schlesinger et al. (Schlesinger et al., 2015) and Trullas et al. (Trullas et al., 2018). The information was analyzed with the statistical software R version 3.5.1 using the Llavaan, Sem, Semplot packages.

2.1. Research design

The methodology was developed with an empirical, nonexperimental, cross-sectional, causal research design. To identify how higher education management innovates to build brand identity, the study follows a quantitative methodology through the application of surveys in the second semester of 2019 to the teachers of seven accredited universities in Colombia. The participants were selected via convenience sampling (Etikan et al., 2016), a nonprobability sampling that involved a population of 367 teachers. In the end, 231 teachers completed the questionnaire. The survey scale was designed based on the study by Deshpande (Deshpande, 1996), which employed a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree). This scale was contrasted in different studies carried out by renowned academics (Schlesinger et al., 2015; Trullas et al., 2018).

Table 1 presents the main variables of the research and the key studies that have supported the construction of the questionnaire.

The data obtained were analyzed by CFA and structural equation modelling (SEM) (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988; Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Jöreskog, 1993; Ruiz et al., 2010; Schlesinger et al., 2015, 2017; Trullas et al., 2018) using the statistical software R version 3.5.1 and the Llavaan, SEM, and Semplot packages following different statistical techniques that offered scale validity and study reliability (Ruiz et al., 2010).

2.2. Data collection

The 231 teachers surveyed in the study belong to high-quality private and public universities accredited by the Ministry of Education of Colombia. A total of 4.8% of the teachers surveyed had completed post-doctoral studies, 26% were in the process of completing their PhDs, 56% were completing master's degrees, 11% were in the specialization process and 3% were working on undergraduate degrees.

Regarding the ages of the teachers, 28% were 50 years old or older, 36% were between 40 and 49 years old, 33% were between 30 and 39 years old, and 5% were between 20 and 29 years old. Table 2 summarizes the number of respondents by university. Thus, two universities represent almost 50% of the total responses. The number of responses was classified by sex and length of employment (more than one year for this analysis). The findings reveal that, in general, accredited universities in Colombia have good recruitment and retention strategies, thus ensuring the stability of the faculty.

3. Results

Using correlations and internal consistency, the one-dimensionality and reliability of each item were examined to validate the measurement scales used in the instrument. The internal consistency coefficient was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha and the exploratory confirmatory factor analysis technique for clarity. In addition, the KMO was followed as a criterion (Kaiser, 1974) to evaluate the representativeness of the sample (see Table 3).

The previous values of the KMO test, in terms of the scale proposed by Kaiser, correspond to the factors of the research project at meritorious and satisfactory values since they are higher than 0.80 (Cerny & Kaiser, 1977). Thus, these values indicate the representativeness of the sample in each item analyzed. With the values obtained, it is thus established that the factorial analysis technique is viable in estimating the dimensions that make up the proposed structural model.

Regarding the values of the measures associated with the reliability and validity of the scale, Table 4 presents the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, the composite reliability and the extracted variance index called the average of extracted variance (AVE) for each factor. Thus, all the values satisfy the main

Table 1. Instrument and theoretical references.

	THEORETICAL REFERENCE
1. UNIVERSITY EDUCATION MARKETING	
1. The university has innovative management models that contribute to institutional marketing strategies.	(Oplatka, 2004)
2. The university has a work team for the institutional marketing area or department.	(Oplatka, 2017)
3. The educational marketing strategies implemented by the university are known.	(Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2006)
4. The university's marketing team considers the role of teachers in creating valuable strategies	(James et al., 2018)
5. University teachers are involved in marketing strategies to promote the university brand.	
6. The university is successful in generating strategies to attract and maintain human talent.	
2. RELATIONAL MARKETING – TRUST	
1. The university is perceived as a sincere and honest organization.	(Frasquet et al., 2012)
2. The university acts with integrity, demonstrating morality and honesty.	(R. S. Fernández et al., 2011)
3. The university's administration can be trusted.	(Schlesinger et al., 2015)
4. The university is expected to act correctly in its management of academics.	(Morgan & Hunt, 1994)
5. Teachers perceive that this university has been on their side to ensure jobs and well-being.	(Schlesinger et al., 2017)
6. The university communicates its mission, vision, and values frankly.	(Liu et al., 2016)
7. Teachers at this university are competent in their jobs.	
8. It is possible to speak freely about labor difficulties within the university.	
9. The directors at the university respond constructively when there is a labor disagreement.	
10. 16. Ideas and feelings can be freely shared within the university.	
3. RELATIONAL MARKETING – SATISFACTION	
1. Being in college has been successful for your professional growth.	(Schlesinger et al., 2015)
2. Your experience at the university has met your expectations.	(Fornell & Larcker, 1981)
3. You are satisfied with the university.	(R. S. Fernández et al., 2011)
4. The university fulfils what it promises to its teachers.	(Schlesinger et al., 2017)
5. The time and effort that a teacher dedicates to the relationship with the university has been worth it.	(Frasquet et al., 2012)
6. University managers attend to the needs of teachers.	(Trullas et al., 2018)
7. If there is any difficulty that requires talking to someone in university management, it will be properly attended to.	(Wei & Junyan, 2015)
8. If there is any difficulty that requires talking to someone from faculty management, it will be properly attended to.	
9. The directors are concerned about keeping the teachers satisfied at the university.	
10. In general, you are satisfied with the university's management team.	
11. In general, you are satisfied with the faculty management team.	
12. You consider that you are well paid as a teacher at the university.	
13. The university provides you with sufficient comforts to achieve your full development as a teacher.	
4. RELATIONAL MARKETING – LOYALTY	
1. If you had to choose this university again to carry out your teaching, you would choose it again.	(Schlesinger et al., 2017)
2. If someone asks you to recommend the university, you do.	(Schlesinger et al., 2015)
3. You would recommend the university to a colleague seeking to become part of the teaching staff.	(Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001)
4. If the opportunity arose, you would share positive things about the university with your friends and family.	(Cervera et al., 2012)
5. If you had to take professional development courses, this university would be your first choice.	(R. S. Fernández et al., 2011)
6. You would encourage family and friends to study or be part of this university.	(Trullas et al., 2018)
7. You value your relationship with other teachers at this university.	
8. You believe that the university creates a good environment for the personal and professional promotion of teachers.	
9. The university encourages the generation of academic and research networks among teachers.	
10. The university recognizes and values teacher achievements (for example, an award, a good academic result).	

Source: By authors 2022.

Table 2. Sample.

University	Answers	%	Gender	
			F/M	Hiring
U1	9	3.89%	6/3	88.88%
U2	62	26.83%	34/28	100%
U3	82	35.49%	34/48	97.59%
U4	16	6.92%	11/5	100%
U5	35	15.15%	14/21	97.14%

Source: By authors 2022.

Table 3. KMO results.

Factor	Institutional marketing	Relational marketing (trust)	Relational marketing (satisfaction)	Relational marketing (loyalty)
Value	0.85	0.82	0.89	0.85

Source: By authors 2022.

Table 4. Reliability and reliability measures of the scale.

Factor	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
Institutional marketing	0.869	0.927	0.532
Relational marketing	0.957	0.953	0.474

Source: By authors 2022.

assumptions of reliability and one-dimensionality of the scale. Additionally, the correlations of the items for each factor were examined, and it was observed that they have highly positive correlation values greater than or equal to 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Bentler, 2009).

To address the research hypotheses and conduct a detailed comparison of the proposed model, a quantitative study was implemented using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method. This statistical approach allows evaluating the complex relationships between latent variables and measures, providing a deeper understanding of the underlying dynamics in the context of educational management and brand identity construction in universities.

By identifying statistically significant relationships between variables in the proposed model, the relevance of the initially formulated hypotheses is validated. The confirmation of these relationships strengthens the robustness of the conceptual framework and supports the study's contribution to understanding how marketing strategies, teacher satisfaction, and other factors interrelate in the university setting.

Given the sensitive nature of hypothesis testing, especially using the chi-square statistic in relation to sample size, a corrective measure is implemented to address possible distortions. This approach ensures the reliability of the results, allowing a more accurate interpretation of statistical significance and consolidating the study's validity in methodological terms. Together, this robust methodological approach provides a comprehensive foundation for evaluating the proposed relationships in the conceptual model and significantly contributes to knowledge in the field of educational management and university marketing.

The variables under study, such as marketing strategies, teacher satisfaction, and other key factors, maintain intricate and significant relationships in the university context. The implementation of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis allows unraveling these connections, confirming the relevance of the initially formulated hypotheses. The interaction between marketing strategies and teacher perception directly influences the university's brand identity. The corrective measure adopted ensures statistical robustness in evaluating these relationships, consolidating the methodological and conceptual contribution of the study to the comprehensive understanding of educational management and university marketing.

$$\left| \frac{\chi^2}{df} \right| = 3.6066 \quad \left| \frac{\chi^2}{df} \right| = 3.6066$$

Regarding institutional marketing, the following relationship is used:

$$\left| \frac{\chi^2}{df} \right| = 1.7747 \quad \left| \frac{\chi^2}{df} \right| = 1.7747$$

This corrective measure is called the absolute goodness-of-fit measure and determines the degree to which the general model predicts the correlation matrix. The main measures of goodness of fit are presented below in Table 5. In addition, it is indicated that the values of the previous relationship should take a value less than or equal to 5 to obtain an adequate goodness of fit to the model. Based on previous studies, the absolute fit of a model was also evaluated through the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) measure, offering acceptable values in this investigation (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988).

Table 5. Goodness-of-fit measures: Structural equation model (SEM).

Factor		df	p value	cfi	rmsea	lfi
Higher education management	7.099	4	0.131	0.995	0.058	0.995
Relational marketing	1543.653	428	0.000	0.778	0.106	0.780

Source: By authors 2022.

Table 6. Sociodemographic characteristics of the universities.

University	Total records	%	Gender		Length of employment greater than 1 year
			F	M	
U1	9	3.89%	6	3	88.88%
U2	62	26.83%	34	28	100%
U3	82	35.49%	34	48	97.59%
U4	16	6.92%	11	5	100%
U5	35	15.15%	14	21	97.14%
U6	7	3.03%	3	4	66.66%
U7	20	8.65%	7	13	100%
TOTAL	231	100%	109	122	–

Source: By authors 2022.

The SEM system was used to examine the impact of possible relationships between dimensions, factors, constructs, and latent variables of interest. The hypotheses presented above could be confirmed. One of the advantages of using SEM is that this technique allows establishing the dependency relationship between the variables and integrates a series of equations that have an associated measurement error. Thus, the relationships can be established in multiple ways between the variables (Jöreskog, 1993).

3.1. Implications of the results

The results were classified from the characterization of the population that made up the sample, followed by the way in which marketing management is perceived in the universities studied. Additionally, the behavior of the interviewees was evidenced by the marketing strategies with a relational approach that the universities implemented to generate value. Finally, a method was proposed to involve teachers in university management to allow building and/or strengthening the brand identity in 1) sociodemographic characterization, 2) university management, 3) relational marketing and 4) innovative proposals to build brands and manage knowledge.

3.1.1. Sociodemographic characterization

Next, a general description of the sample that was part of the study is provided. All the teachers surveyed were employed by private and public universities with high-quality accreditation by the Ministry of Education of Colombia (Table 6). Of the participants, 4.8% were postdoctoral employees, 26% had doctorate degrees, 56% had some doctorate training 11% had specialized training and 3% had only undergraduate degrees. A total of 28% of the teachers were 50 years old or older, 36% were between 40 and 49 years old, 33% were between 30 and 39 years old, and 5% were between 20 and 29 years old. Table 1 summarizes the number of respondents per university. The number of responses was classified by gender and length of employment, which for this analysis was greater than one year. The results indicate that the universities use good recruitment and retention strategies to ensure the stability of the faculty.

3.1.2. University management

When asked about their universities' management of marketing strategies, teachers identified their work commitment as key content, which is reflected in Hypothesis 1. Such marketing strategies achieve greater visibility and recognition for its teachers. However, the teachers surveyed do not consider themselves, for the most part, involved in the strategies developed by their institutions' marketing staff, nor do they fully understand the value of their teaching, research, and reputations. Teachers know little about marketing campaigns designed to build trust, satisfaction, and loyalty, and this is evidenced in the result of rejection of Hypothesis 2.

Table 7. Structural equation model: Analysis of causal relationships and hypothesis testing.

Hypothesis	Structural relationship	Stand. load	Stand load/z value
H1 Accepted	University - Institutional Marketing	1.249	(0.107) ***
H2 Rejected	Institutional Marketing - Teacher	0.293	(0.166)
H3 Accepted	Teacher - Relational marketing	0.229	(0.043) ***
H4 Accepted	Trust - Satisfaction	0.586	(0.096) ***
H5 Accepted	Satisfaction to loyalty	1.070	(0.160) ***

Source: By authors 2022.

To find a significant relationship between the constructs, SEM was used to confirm the hypotheses. One of the characteristics for which the modelling was used was to verify the dependency relationship between the relationship marketing variables and the way they affect university management. For this reason, Table 7 shows the standard load/z value and the result for each one of the hypotheses; the diagrams from the software *** show the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses.

3.1.3. Relational marketing

The strategies implemented by the analyzed universities are representative of components that generate marketing with a relational approach, as evidenced by the results of Hypotheses 3, 4 and 5 of Table 7. When accepted, the teachers perceive that marketing is performed by their universities and that concepts have been incorporated that facilitate the development of long-term relationships.

Likewise, Hypothesis 4 is accepted; teachers perceive universities as honest and sincere in their management models and that they support their work and well-being and consider their concerns and disagreements, which in turn leads to job satisfaction. Likewise, the results of Hypothesis 5 show that teachers believe that universities have taken actions that make them feel confident and satisfied, so that they will remain for a long time and generate value in the articulation of institutional projects.

The results show that teachers feel satisfied in their workplaces, that universities provide sufficient comfort and that teachers feel they are contributing to the academic community and society.

3.1.4. Innovation in marketing to build a brand and manage knowledge

The innovation in this research is the effort to intentionally involve teachers in marketing management so that the university brand is based on better communication and a more correct corporate image and reputation.

One of the most important factors in organizations is good corporate identity management (Kapferer, 1992; Orozco-Toro, 2018; Riel, 1997; Tajada, 1994; Toro, 2009; Vire Riascos, 2019). In this sense, it is necessary for universities to manage this identity in the best possible way, which will allow them to improve their branding (Aaker, 2002; Ávalos, 2010; Brujó, 2010; Fernández et al., 2009; Hatch & Schultz, 2010). For this reason, Figure 2 shows the path that can serve as support for universities to consider the teacher as a means of motivating and inspiring students, graduates, coworkers, and in general, all of those with whom they meet.

In this management scheme, the role of the teacher is not only to transmit knowledge or guide a process or accompany a group of learners but also to contribute significantly to the university, which provides opportunities for personal and professional growth. In this research, due to the great influence that teachers have in universities, they can be considered as the foundation on which to build and strengthen the university brand. Thus, to improve branding, innovation in the management of universities must be based on a corporate identity promoted via relational marketing and with teachers as the central axis.

3.1.5. Limitations

Although the methodology used in this study is robust, it is important to acknowledge its limitations that could affect the interpretation of the results. Firstly, the participants were selected through convenience sampling, which may introduce bias in the sample and limit the generalizability of the results to

Figure 2. Management scheme in universities for brand building and knowledge management.

the entire university population. The study's focus on high-quality universities in Colombia may limit the applicability of the findings to different educational contexts.

Additionally, the reliance on participants' self-assessment through surveys is a limitation. While validated measurement scales were used, subjective interpretation by respondents could affect the accuracy of the responses. Moreover, it is important to note that the study was conducted solely during the second semester of 2019, which may not accurately reflect any changes in university dynamics over time.

The sample composition, with a higher percentage of responses from certain universities, could potentially impact the representativeness of the conclusions. Furthermore, the limited diversity in terms of age and gender of the participants may restrict the generalizability of the results to more diverse university contexts.

Despite the limitations, this study offers valuable insight into the dynamics of marketing and management in higher education institutions. It is important to consider these constraints when interpreting and applying the results in various educational settings.

3.1.6. Theoretical implications

The research results have significant theoretical implications for university management and relational marketing in higher education. The validation of the measurement scales, using techniques such as Cronbach's alpha coefficient and confirmatory factor analysis, supports the reliability and one-dimensionality of the dimensions proposed in the structural model. The KMO measure's meritorious and satisfactory values reinforce the sample's representativeness and the viability of the factor analysis technique to estimate the model's dimensions.

The positive correlation coefficients highlight the internal consistency and relational between the constructs evaluated in the research, such as institutional marketing and relational marketing focused on trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. The scales demonstrate high reliability and one-dimensionality, as evidenced by the Cronbach coefficients and AVE, supporting the internal consistency and convergent validity of the measurements.

The SEM analysis confirms the relationships proposed in the initial hypotheses, reinforcing the relevance of the variables analyzed in the context of university management and relational marketing. Higher education management has a significant impact on institutional marketing strategies and relational marketing, confirming their connection. Additionally, the importance of building and maintaining strong relationships in the academic community is highlighted by the significant relationship between relationship marketing dimensions and the satisfaction and loyalty of different stakeholders.

In synthesis, the theoretical implications of this study suggest that effective management in higher education, combined with well-articulated marketing strategies, can be crucial for strengthening the brand identity of educational institutions. The empirical validation of these relationships provides a solid basis for future research and contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the field of university management and educational marketing.

3.1.7. Practical implications

The results of this study have practical implications for effective management in higher education. The validation of the measurement scales and confirmation of proposed relationships emphasize the importance of implementing institutional and relational marketing strategies in universities. Those responsible

for educational management can benefit from focusing on building a strong brand identity. This can attract and retain students, teachers, and other stakeholders.

The significant relationship between higher education management and marketing strategies suggests that an efficient and innovation-focused administration can catalyze the success of marketing initiatives. University leaders should integrate innovative and creative practices into educational management to build and maintain brand identity.

Strong relationships in the academic community are crucial for stakeholder satisfaction and loyalty, as evidenced by the positive connection between relational marketing and these outcomes. Universities can benefit from adopting approaches that promote trust, satisfaction, and loyalty among students, faculty, and other collaborators. Strategies that facilitate interaction and effective communication can be key to establishing and maintaining lasting relationships.

This study suggests that universities should invest in staff training and development, with a focus on marketing and interpersonal skills. This could enhance the efficacy of marketing tactics and reinforce the relationship with diverse stakeholders.

4. Discussion of the results

This research addresses a relevant issue in the field of higher education, highlighting the lack of understanding and effective application of marketing in universities, focusing on improving satisfaction, retention, lasting relationships, and brand identity, as well as promoting creativity and innovation in education (Gómez-Bayona et al., 2019). The choice to examine how higher education management innovates to build brand identity provides a valuable and timely approach to the management carried out by universities in both developed and developing countries (Gómez-Bayona & Arrubla-Zapata, 2020).

A significant finding is the prominent importance of incorporating teachers as a key factor in the implementation of relational marketing strategies in higher education management (Gómez-Bayona et al., 2020) to improve communication aspects that allow, as mentioned by Van Riel and Balmer (1997), building identity and image to enhance university reputation conditions. Since teachers are key figures in the students' academic experience and act as ambassadors of the institution, a positive identity, supported by a strong image, contributes to generating trust among students, parents, and the community at large (Zhao, 2010).

Additionally, a positive image strengthens institutional reputation, which can attract talented students, improve student retention, and foster collaboration with other institutions and academic partners. Teachers, being an integral part of this image, directly influence how academic quality and institutional commitment are perceived.

From an internal perspective, a positive identity can increase morale and job satisfaction among teachers. An environment where professors are proud of their institution and recognize its commitment to academic excellence tends to generate a greater sense of belonging and motivation. This revelation underscores the need to recognize and leverage the strategic role of teachers in building university brand identity (Lizote et al., 2019). To develop a marketing culture and brand identity, as these are fundamental aspects that can serve as practical guidance for educational institutions.

The marketing and the brand of universities is the basis for their position in society, and value is the basis for scaling marketing efforts. Therefore, universities seeking to build their brand, must increase their influence and appeal in society. The value of the brand can be measured by various means, such as academic reputation or the quality of teachers (Li & Gong, 2022). This reflects the fundamental role that teachers play in brand building. Thus, branding is a strategic issue for universities, although it is not completely clear how universities develop and manage brand strategies. Spry et al. (Spry et al., 2020) found that a strong teaching brand that is jointly designed and developed through values related to teachers and shared by staff and external partners is an effective way to manage an emerging university brand.

Knowledge management is a necessary process for the professional competencies of teachers. Such processes allow teachers and, therefore, universities to evolve in a global society driven by networked information. This is because in an economy based on knowledge, management facilitates learning and improves the professional development of teachers and, therefore, training processes in institutions,

creating a university precedent that fosters brand equity (Zhao, 2010). Based on this, the fact that teachers are the fundamental basis for brand building and knowledge management is supported.

Human capital is increasingly important for organizations, especially in the case of universities and higher education institutions, whose basic raw material is intelligence, for academic production. Therefore, aspects such as teacher autonomy, professional growth opportunities, planning, and diversity, among others, should be considered. Previous studies have shown that teachers need to be motivated and engaged. Therefore, universities are called upon to operationalize internal marketing from a strategic approach to the management of human resources to align the human resources strategy with the organization's strategy (Lizote et al., 2019).

Taking this into account, a limited number of studies have been aimed at university management for brand building and knowledge management based on teachers. Few internal marketing studies consider internal communication, training and development, interrelationships, motivation, rewards, work support and the loyalty of collaborators (Sahibzada et al., 2019). This study addresses the importance of university management from teacher-centered relational marketing for identity management, brand building and knowledge management based on satisfaction, loyalty, and trust. Therefore, this study makes a theoretical contribution to innovation in university management based on relational management in the context of a developing country. This type of marketing strategy is applicable in other contexts.

This study found that there is an opportunity for universities to make informed decisions regarding brand building and knowledge management with the support of their teachers. Brand-oriented marketing strategies in higher education institutions should solicit the input of teachers so that they can contribute to institutional marketing and are able to help build a greater relationship with management as well as brand value.

5. Conclusions

According to the results obtained in this study, more work is required in the areas of institutional marketing to better understand the concept of marketing in universities. Currently, the responsibility of marketing is the entire university as an organization, and all interest groups are called upon to participate in proposals that provide better satisfaction in administrative and academic processes. Focusing on achieving a transaction from the service portfolio of stakeholders should not be the intent. Instead, what is truly strategic is to build a culture of service that has as its main focus the long-term relationship and recognition of university stakeholders. Individuals are in constant search of experiences and the ability to share them in the family, work and even global environments. Thus, it is the responsibility of all to generating these experiences that provide visibility and organizational positioning.

Although teachers recognize that marketing strategies are devised to recruit new prospects, it is necessary to work on strengthening the strategies within the universities to retain the natural market that is available because it is more economical to retain the current human talent than to hire new employees. The majority of teachers do not feel involved in the management processes of marketing. For this reason, they do not know the functionality of this discipline in the tasks that they perform on a day-to-day basis. Likewise, it can be concluded that the marketing strategies that the different institutions incorporate should consider the inclusion of the teaching body as one of the most important interest groups in promoting the university. Teachers can significantly permeate the way in which students conceptualize the university and have a very large impact on marketing derived from the relationships that occur within the classrooms.

Higher education institutions should guide part of the development of their marketing actions in the management of identity as a conducive way for the correct administration of the brand. In this regard, actions related to relationship marketing, innovation, and identity management will be the key so that, through teachers, the image and corporate reputation of the universities can be improved, which will ultimately result in building a brand. It is expected that universities understand the importance of marketing with a relational approach in academic settings and that the results of this study may be the starting point for further exploration of building trust, satisfaction, and loyalty to contribute to the administrative and academic management of universities. Further, the teacher is strategic in marketing,

and they should have greater clarity about how important they are in the marketing strategies and tactics that are proposed to generate value.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Ethical approval

All participants were provided with consents that highlight their voluntary participation, how the data will be used in the research and how their confidentiality will be maintained during and after the study.

Consent to participate

Consents were obtained from the participants' parents to maintain the ethical standards within this study.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, upon reasonable request.

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